

Abdulla Avloniy's "Turkiy Guliston or Morality" in the Eyes of Today's Youth

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Abstract: This article attempts to analyze and reveal the significance of Abdulla Avloni, one of our devoted intellectuals who worked for the freedom of the nation and the future of the country, and his work "Turkiy Guliston or Morality" in both the last century and today. It explores the influence of the work on society and its role in the upbringing of youth.

Keywords: Turkestan, Jadid, nation, morality, upbringing, cleanliness, superstition, science, geometry, textbook, teacher, strategy, renaissance.

History is like a book that holds many secrets. The past century was a time of great trials for our country and our people. During this period, many individuals who were ready to give their lives for the homeland perished. This was a great loss for the Uzbek nation. The fact that individuals dedicated to the future of the nation were executed as traitors to the country was a major tragedy for the 20th century.

From the late 19th century, the Jadid movement began to spread widely in Central Asia. The main goal of this movement was to educate the people and cleanse Turkestan from backwardness and religious superstitions. The representatives of this movement fought bravely until their last drop of blood. One of these intellectuals was Abdulla Avloni. He was born on July 12, 1878, in the Mergancha neighborhood of Tashkent.¹ From a young age, he had a strong interest in knowledge. Despite being small, he never stopped learning, especially showing a keen interest in literature. In 1904, he founded a Jadid-style school in Murobod.² Abdulla Avloni, who made it his primary goal to educate the nation's youth, not only opened schools but also worked on creating textbooks for students. He quickly published works such as "Birinci Muallim" (The First Teacher), "Ikkinchi Muallim" (The Second Teacher), and "Turkiy Guliston or Morality". Although new textbooks were being developed for the new method schools, students were still taught books like Saidrasul Azizi's "Ustozi Avval" (The First Mentor) and Munavvarqori's "Adibi Avval" (The First Literary Expert).³

The first edition of "Turkiy Guliston or Morality", a shining example of Uzbek pedagogy, was published in 1913 in Tashkent. From today's perspective, the work holds a deep and powerful meaning. This book, used as a textbook for the new method schools of the 20th century, served as a foundational guide for the upbringing of the emerging younger generation. In general, the

¹ Jadidlar. Abdulla Avloniy. Olim Oltinbek. Yoshlar nashriyot uyi. Toshkent. 2022. 4-bet.

² Abdulla Avloniy. "Afg'oniston sayohati" (Afgan Journeys). "Sharq yulduzi" journal, 1990. Page-7.

³ Jadidlar. Abdulla Avloniy. Olim Oltinbek. Yoshlar nashriyot uyi. Toshkent-2022. 36-bet

essence of Avloni's textbooks, like "Birinch Muallim" (The First Teacher) and "Ikkinchi Muallim" (The Second Teacher), was also focused primarily on education.

Why was the role of upbringing central to Avloni's works? The author himself beautifully explains this in "Turkiy Guliston or Morality". He emphasizes: "Since we are lazy and inexperienced, and because we have not received upbringing from our mothers at home, moral education from our teachers, and scientific education from our tutors, we cannot benefit from government schools either".⁴ In fact, Avloni's words were absolutely relevant to the environment of that time. This is because education primarily begins in the family. If the necessary conditions for an individual to grow into a complete person are not created in the family, this could be a tragedy that undermines the future of the nation. Indeed, our first education comes from our mothers. If mothers are not educated, then their children will also lack the desire to gain knowledge and strive to become morally mature individuals because this feeling has not been instilled in them.

One of our enlightened forefathers, Mahmudkhodja Behbudi, said: "In developed nations, it is the mothers who educate. Therefore, we must first educate our mothers and teach them language, as our ignorance and lack of language stem from them. Do not leave the children of Turkestan uneducated".⁵ Abdulla Avloni also emphasized this topic in his work "Turkiy Guliston or Morality". During a time when religious fanaticism was strong, promoting such ideas and instilling them in the minds of the youth was a mark of great courage.

Today, the ideas and thoughts put forward by our intellectuals have become some of the most relevant topics. Our nation's leader has created every opportunity for women to receive education and become skilled professionals. Regarding this, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the ceremonial event dedicated to International Women's Day on March 7, 2023, said: "When a single girl in a family receives an education, earns a higher degree, and acquires a modern profession, the entire atmosphere of the household changes".⁶ This shows that the ideas and plans formed by the representatives of the Jadid movement in the 20th century have now started to bear fruit.

In "Turkiy Guliston or Morality", in addition to the issues mentioned above, there is also an emphasis on scientific knowledge and instructions. The work connects science directly with education and behavior, and its essence lies in this integration. This book, primarily used for upper and graduating classes, contains instructions not only for students but also for teachers. In the chapter titled "Moral Education," the following lines are included: "Therefore, the teachers who are responsible for education must themselves practice what they teach and ensure that their lessons are accompanied by actions when teaching their students. In this way, the knowledge and lessons taught will quickly affect the hearts of students, and they will become moral scholars".⁷

These thoughts put forward the idea that moral behavior should be exemplified not only by the learners but also by the teachers. The book does not limit itself to education and upbringing; it also discusses cleanliness (nazofat). It emphasizes that a sharp mind thrives in a clean environment and explains that neglecting cleanliness can lead to health problems, including various skin diseases.

⁴ Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq. Abdulla Avloniy. Toshkent "O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi". Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti 2004. 6-7-betlar. 5. [https://: parliament.gov.uz](https://parliament.gov.uz)

⁵ [https://: gazeta.uz](https://gazeta.uz).

⁶ Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq. Abdulla Avloniy. Toshkent "O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi". Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti 2004. 10-bet.

⁷ Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq. Abdulla Avloniy. Toshkent "O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi". Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti 2004. 10-bet.

As you know, the last century saw the rise of religious superstitions in our country. Naturally, this situation directly hindered the activities of new-method schools. Religious scholars even went as far as accusing the intellectuals of heresy. Despite these circumstances, Abdulla Avloni worked to ensure that young people were exposed to both religious and secular sciences. In his work, he emphasized this by saying: “To be a religious person, it is necessary not only to study religious sciences but also to know scientific fields such as mathematics, geometry, history, philosophy, chemistry, medicine, and agriculture, in order to become a true scholar”.⁸

This shows that, despite the challenging political climate, Avloni was able to create opportunities for youth to receive education. His textbooks were not only used in Turkestan but also in neighboring countries. Avloni witnessed this firsthand during his official visit to Afghanistan, where he was pleased to see that his textbooks were being used as primary teaching materials in schools in Kabul.⁹

In “Turkiy Guliston or Morality”, Abdulla Avloni successfully integrated all the qualities necessary for an individual’s moral and intellectual development. The title of the book, “Turkiy Guliston or Morality”, was not chosen by chance. In the second edition of the book, Avloni wrote: “It became clear to me, as I was among the teachers, that there was no comprehensive ‘Morality’ book written in our Turkic dialect for the schools of Turkestan, and that the people were thirsty for and in need of such a work. After much experience, I considered it my sacred duty to write such a work in the style of the esteemed writer Sheikh Saadi, despite the difficulty of the task, to eliminate this shortcoming”.¹⁰

In modern Uzbekistan, there has been a significant resurgence of interest in the activities of the Jadid intellectuals. Extensive opportunities have been created to study the lives of our ancestors who sacrificed their lives for the freedom and future of the nation. During the expanded meeting of the National Spirituality and Enlightenment Council on December 22, 2023, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, expressed the following views: “Whether someone likes it or not, our people must continue on the path shown by our Jadid forefathers, because their ideas and programs are in full harmony with the strategy of building a New Uzbekistan”.¹¹

In conclusion, the aforementioned views clearly show that the youth of the 21st century are actively studying the lives and works of these intellectuals and drawing their own conclusions.¹² As a result, various proposals and analyses have begun to emerge among the youth. For example, how appropriate would it be to promote “Turkiy Guliston or Morality”, which was taught to senior students in new-method schools, among today’s youth? Of course, the answers to this question may vary, as different people approach the issue from different perspectives.¹³

In my opinion, the work contains deep insights related to education and upbringing. From today’s standpoint, the work is an essential resource for the education and especially the upbringing of every Uzbek child. Indeed, the foundation of the Third Renaissance lies in the hands of the youth. I believe that the moral principles outlined in this work can easily attract

⁸ Abdulla Avloniy. “Afg’oniston sayohati” (Afgan Journeys). “Sharq yulduzi” journal, 1990. Page-7.

⁹ Abdulla Avloniy. Tanlangan asarlar. Begali Qosimov. Toshkent “Ma’naviyat” 2009. 48-bet.

¹⁰ “Jadid” gazetasi. “Sharq” nashriyat matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosmaxonasi. 2024-yil 1- yanvar. 2-bet.

¹¹ Kamolov, J. M., & Shozamonova, L. (2023). USMONIYLAR SULOLASI VAKILLARINING EPETETLARI. RESEARCH AND EDUCATION, 2(5), 175-181.

¹² Камолов, Ж. М., & Рахматова, М. Ш. (2022). ЭФТАЛИЙЛАРДА ДАВЛАТ МАФКУРАСИ ВА ХУҚУҚ ТИЗИМИ. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES (Vol. 1, No. 21, pp. 238-242).

¹³ Kamolov, J. M., & Murtazayeva, F. O. (2024). FRANSIYA QIROLLARI TARIXGA NAZAR (qirollar epitetlari misolida, Frantsiya, V-Xasrlar). Thematic Journal of Applied Sciences, 4(2).

the attention of students. To achieve a new Renaissance, it is essential to follow the path of those who laid the foundation for it.

Our thoughts are being validated today. The efforts of our intellectuals, who gave their lives for the nation's future, have not gone unnoticed. Under the initiative of our President, from the 2020/2021 academic year for grades 1-9, and from the 2021/2022 academic year for grades 10-11, "Tarbiya" textbooks have been introduced. In preparing these textbooks, Japan's "Moral Education", Singapore's "Character and Citizenship Education", and the UK's "Thought and Learning" were closely studied, and the ideas of our Jadid ancestors were also incorporated into these textbooks.

In each chapter of the textbook, the enlightening words of our intellectuals and their thoughts on the development of education and upbringing are included. The ideas of European and Turkestan intellectuals were combined to create a comprehensive textbook. This shows that the new "Tarbiya" textbooks have become a unique and modern method of presenting Abdulla Avloni's "Turkiy Guliston or Morality" to students in the 21st century. This approach has been well-received by students, as it not only increases their interest in the activities of the Jadids but also plays a crucial role in shaping the younger generation into morally upright and well-rounded individuals.

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